

DIGITAL ID

WITH ELECTRONIC
SURVEILLANCE SYSTEM

2017

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Abstract

Multipurpose ID is a combination of a Techno Smart Card carrying a sixteen-digit universal identification number to record the entire life time data of an individual and a touch screen Smart Cell Phone for electronic surveillance. Both the units would work together. **Such a unique system would replace all possible documents procured by an individual during his life time.** Thus, the present innovation would make the life of every individual free from superfluous documentation and would serve as a rescue from practice of forged identity, deception and corruption.

Introduction

There are infinite numbers of documents, IDs, certificates, licenses At each level, one has to procure a series of documents, some of which require periodical renewal. To fetch those documents one comes across long queues, lengthy procedures, bulk formalities, intervention of proxies and agents. Even, during online process, every e-site generates and ask for a new ID and password (Garg, 2016) ^[1]. This is how, instead of making things simple, these documents and online processes make life more complicated and miserable. The government officials are overstrained with applications for Aadhaar, Licenses, Samagra-ID, Ration Card, EPIC, Passport, Bank Pass Books, ATMs, Vehicle Registration, Registries, Reports and so forth. Over and above, verification of these documents, at each level, is another tedious exercise (Garg, 2017) ^[2]. Authorities and citizens play hide & seek infinitely that leads to corruption, suppression of facts; loss of time, energy, working hours and revenue which eventually impairs the economy of the Country.

A great number of countries use biometric ID Cards and methods for identifying their citizens. Some examples are listed below. The cards are mostly used by governments.

Spain: Spain has implemented a social security card with biometrics and a smart card chip for storing information.

United Kingdom: Britain is in the process of establishing a national ID Card that uses biometrics to identify its citizens. Their information is then stored in a large central database accessible to many sectors of the government.

Netherlands: The Netherlands have an automated border crossing system with photo, biometric iris recognition, and a smart card chip.

Malaysia: Malaysia has implemented a national ID that uses biometric fingerprint recognition, smart card chips, and photos.

United States: Many companies use ID Cards that are fitted with biometrics. There

are also several universities that are either thinking about switching over to a biometric ID Card or who already have.

France: Like other countries, France is encouraging the implementation of a National ID Card System that relies on Biometrics. Till Date, no secretarial system or an App has been devised, or universally accepted, to save humanity from gathering one document after another; keeping the stack of papers; making them photocopied; getting attested or verified and so on.

Object

The present communication pertains to a digitally operative Multi-purpose ID Card duly incorporated with an IC. The card shall be provided to one and all, at the time of birth or on the day of Census, with a unique 16-digit universal identification number. The Integrated Circuit or micro-chip would record all substantive data of a citizen; including name of the citizen, date of birth, family details, photograph, biometric details, signatures, bar code, QR-code, Aadhaar, educational progress, extra-academic achievements, employment details, transfers & switch-overs, driving license, vehicle registration, mobile phone, PAN, LPG, bank accounts, financial assets, liabilities, passports, visas, foreign travel, legal & medical record, rewards, punishments and so on.

Obviously, it would replace all possible documents procured by an individual during his life time and save humanity from the practice of forged identity, duplicity and corruption.

Definitions

Multi-purpose ID refers to a Digital ID comprising a 16-digit unique identification number for citizens of India. Alternatively, it can also carry 20-digit universal identification number, unique for all denizens of Earth.

Smart Cell Phone represents any device which can be used for generating an instant OTP or entering Security Pass-word, Biometric details (finger-impressions, retinal-scan) and to track the geographical location of the individual (if required).

Card Reader indicates a gadget that can be used to access the document or information saved in the Multi-purpose ID.

Finger-prints are tiny ridges, whorls and valley patterns on the tip of each finger that are altogether unique.

Genetic Profile refers to detectable nucleotide variation(s) on DNA. Any unique variation in number of repeats can be traced through mini-satellites.

Retina comprises an intricate network of blood capillaries that can be captured as an image by means of a high definition camera or scanner casting a low beam of IR light. It can be converted and saved into a database using appropriate algorithms.

Thermal Map denotes IR radiations (about 12 microns) emitted by a human body to distinguish between man and a robot.

Security

Just as all financial transactions take place across hundreds of financial institutions, thousands of business premises, just from a single ATM or bank account, notwithstanding any geographical or political boundaries; likewise, all official notifications, from different administrative organizations, can be chronicled in an appropriate device. As a result, all utilitarian information of the citizen would be available on one click. No concealment, no fraudulence and no duplicity.

The Card would be triply secured through an alpha-numeric password, fingerprints and retinal scan of the bearer.

Operative Mechanism

At the time of birth, the Registrar, Births & Deaths would record the birth details and provide a 16-digit unique digital identification number (UDIN) to the new born baby. The Multi-purpose ID would carry his name, a QR Code and his photograph as depicted in Figure-1.

Figure - 1 : An Outline of Multi-purpose ID
(installed with SIM for digital operation)

The Family details viz. name of the child, date of birth, place, parents' name, address, caste, and so on; together with Genetic and Biometric Information (DNA Map, Finger Impressions, Retinal image, Blood Group etc. as per feasibility) of the child shall be saved online, on the given UDIN. The biometric details would be updated after every five years till he attains 15.

Now, wherever he moves, may it be to school, medical center, job or market, this Multi-purpose ID with 16-digit code number would serve as his roll number,

enrollment number, registration number, bank account number, driving license number, vehicle registration number, mobile number, LPG gas number No additional number would be required for any purpose (except user ID or password, wherever applicable) so all remarkable accomplishments, viz. participations, scholastic grades, add-ons, extra-curricular attainments, sports, etc. of the candidate would be recorded on the same UDIN.

On seeking transfer from one institution to another, the previous school would deactivate his UDIN link from the school portal and as soon as he takes admission in the successive institution, his UDIN would be re-activated and connected with the new institution. This is how a candidate would never be able to take admission in two institutions at a time.

On attaining maturity, the individual would automatically get the right to vote. Even in this case, he would not require any separate EPIC. Since the electoral roll would fetch the data of those who have attained 18 on day-to-day basis, no extra procedure would be required. On the day of polling, any bearer of Multi-purpose ID (who has attained 18) can go to any kiosk, anywhere in India and swipe the card. The kiosk machine would identify his constituency (on the basis of local address, existing in his ID) and after verification of password, allow him to cast his vote.

For procuring passport, PAN, driving license, one can visit the concerning official website; log in with his UDIN; fill the form electronically; fix an appointment, if an interface meeting is required; and get all his biometrics done (photograph, retinal scan, fingerprints).

For barely a few services like passport, where document may be essential in paper form for visa or immigration procedures, there seems to be no valid argument for having a hard copy. This will simplify the procurement procedures too. As soon as the document is digitally signed by the authority, the endorsement would appear on the citizen's profile. Since most of the services would be available online; clerks or proxies will get seldom opportunity to make delays or expect bribes.

If one visits a hospital, either as an outdoor patient or gets hospitalized, all chronic and major ailments shall be entered into his UDIN profile so that he should not be able to deceive medical or insurance authorities for dishonest claims. At the same time, doctors would be able to study the entire medical history of the patient at one go. This will help the patients to get better treatment.

Since your UDIN and all bank account numbers would be same, it would be a matter of seconds to get the details of all deposits and borrowings at one click. Wherever you go, be it a restaurant, club, shopping mall or fly abroad, UDIN would carry statement of every penny you earn or spend. This would enable honest tax

payer to display all his assets & liabilities before the IT authority. Even the IT authorities would have no reason to doubt his integrity. However, dishonest tax payers would have bad days.

Since the number would be protected by password as well as biometric impression, only the individual himself or a competent authority, duly appointed as per provisions of the constitution, shall have right to make access to the record. The remaining information would appear 'masked'.

Since the 16-digit number would be the lone digital identity of the person, he would have no official existence without his Multi-purpose ID. Rather, this Universal Identification Number (UDIN) would replace his christened name. The documents would be treated as anonymous and invalid without this digital number.

Once it is made mandatory for every individual to carry Multi-purpose ID, people will never dare to steal or swap their card with others as all the cards are password protected and carries his biometric details. And if the same is combined with Smart Cell Phone carrying individual's thermal spectrum, they will not be able to detach the card from themselves for long. With this, the possibilities of fake individuality, impersonation, duplicity or concealment of information would reduce to minimum.

Even in case of anti-national activities or offense, it would take a split of second to establish the identity of a suspect/criminal. The information may be uploaded on Global Positioning System which can easily track the location of the suspect.

Now, if the government imposes a check on cash transactions but for petty purchases like grocery, vegetables, etc. up to a maximum of few thousand INR per day per individual, money-laundering would restrict to a few hundreds (in place of crores & their multiples) and possibilities of unaccounted assets and evasion of tax would start declining.

If somebody loses his Multi-purpose ID, he can request the appropriate authority to issue a clone. This clone will be a vegetative copy (without a single mutation) of the original ID. If an offender tries to fetch a card on someone else's identity, in no case he would be able to carry the Card, modify the information or reap the benefits of other's achievements or assets. Since it carries biometric, genetic & thermal details and since it is connected to Global Positioning System, he/she will be immediately caught by the police. Once caught, his biometric details could be verified and (if found guilty) could be put behind the bars.

On death, the Registrar of Birth & Death shall be informed. He would deactivate the UDIN for further use. In such case, only the legal heir shall be entitled to draw claims through his UDIN.

Apart from saving human resources, time, money and administrative complexities, the stack of files and papers in offices would also be reduced to fractional level. No Xerox, no documentation, no verification and no long queues for day-to-day pursuits. Just go for one click and the entire details of an individual would be available, that too fully genuine. Certainly, every pocket would have this device.

Claims The present idea would :

- Overcome the barriers in procuring official documents ;
- Preserve the details of issuing authority ;
- Secure the documents from tampering ;
- Make all the relevant information available to authorities on one click ;
- Easy access to personal information or original documents, anytime and anywhere, through users' registered mobile number ;
- Doubly protect the records (through password & biometric impressions) ;
- Prevent the loss of government revenue (through evasion of taxes) ;
- Restrain malpractices, corruption and fraudulent ;
- Exponentially increase the economy of the nation ; and
- Last, but outstandingly, make the life simple and hassle-free in real sense.

Thanks To the Honorable Prime Minister of India Mr. Narendra Modi who commended the idea and prompted me to think about India Vision 2020.

To the Ministry of Science & Technology; Earth Science & Vijnana Bharti for having provided an opportunity to share my ideas with scientists, corporate tycoons, policy-makers during India International Science Festival and honored me with Young Scientist Award.

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